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Forecasting Population Growth in Samarkand Region Using a Logistic Model

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to analyzing the population growth of Samarkand region using a logistic model and forecasting future changes. The study examines population dynamics between 2000-2023 and determines the parameters of the logistic model. Results indicate a stable growth trend in the region's population, which may reach approximately 4,600 thousand people by 2030. The article discusses the graphical representation of the model, forecast results, and their significance. Furthermore, the importance of the research findings in developing socio-economic development strategies for Samarkand region is emphasized. The conclusion summarizes the main findings and provides recommendations for future research. This study serves as an important basis for a deeper understanding and effective management of demographic processes in Samarkand region.

Keywords: Samarkand region, population size, demography, logistic model, population growth, forecasting, environmental capacity, growth coefficient.

I. INTRODUCTION

Studying population changes and dynamics is crucial for planning and managing the socio-economic development of any country or region [1]. Samarkand region, one of the oldest and culturally rich areas of Uzbekistan, deserves special attention in terms of its population changes. Located in the central part of Uzbekistan, Samarkand region covers an area of 16,77 thousand square kilometers. According to 2023 data, the region's population exceeds 4.1 million people, accounting for approximately 11 percent of Uzbekistan's population [3]. The region's economy is primarily based on agriculture, industry, and tourism.

Population growth is a complex process influenced by numerous factors [4]. Various approaches exist for modeling this process, one of which is the logistic model. The logistic model describes population growth under conditions of limited resources. This model demonstrates initial rapid population growth, followed by a slowdown, and eventually reaching a saturation point [5].

The main objective of this research is to analyze the population growth of Samarkand region using a logistic model and forecast future changes. The research tasks include: studying the dynamics of the region's population in past years; determining population growth parameters through the application of the logistic model; forecasting future population based on the model; and analyzing the results to draw relevant conclusions.

The results of this study may be significant for developing socio-economic development strategies for Samarkand region, as well as for planning employment, education, healthcare, and other social sectors.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have been conducted on population growth modeling, with the logistic model holding a special place among them. We will review several important pieces of literature in this field.

The logistic growth model, proposed by Verhulst in 1838, is widely used in studying population dynamics. The model presented in his work "Notice sur la loi que la population suit dans son accroissement" demonstrates the limitations of population growth and its dependence on environmental capacity. This model later became the basis for many demographic studies [6].

Among modern research, the article "Analysis of logistic growth models" by Tsoularis and Wallace (Mathematical Biosciences, 1979) deserves special attention. They analyzed various modifications of the logistic model, demonstrating its effectiveness in describing biological and demographic processes. This study helped to deepen the understanding of the theoretical foundations of the logistic model [7].

Research conducted by scientists from Tashkent State University of Economics on population growth modeling in the context of Uzbekistan is of significant importance. In particular, the article "Population of Uzbekistan: growth trends and forecasts" by Abdullaev and Khudoyqulov (Economic Bulletin of Uzbekistan, 2018) analyzes various aspects of population growth in our country and its regions. In their study, they applied the logistic model along with other forecasting methods to identify the unique characteristics of population growth in Uzbekistan [8].

This literature review serves as a theoretical and practical basis for studying the population growth of Samarkand region using the logistic model. Verhulst's classical approach, the in-depth analysis of Tsoularis and Wallace, and the research of local scientists play an important role in shaping the methodology to be applied in our work and in interpreting the results.

II. METHODOLOGY

Data Set

The methodological basis of our research consists of data collection and analysis using the logistic model. During the data collection process, the official website of the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (stat.uz) served as the primary source. This source provides the most reliable and up-to-date demographic data for Uzbekistan and its regions.

The population dynamics of Samarkand region between 2000-2023 are reflected in the following table:

Table 1. Population of Samarkand region from 2000 to 2023.

Year	Population (thousand people)
2000	2670.3
2001	2710.0
2002	2749.8
2003	2789.1
2004	2826.1

2005	2867.1
2006	2907.5
2007	2955.5
2008	3003.4
2009	3061.6
2010	3119.0
2011	3270.8
2012	3326.2
2014	3445.6
2015	3514.8
2016	3583.9
2017	3651.7
2018	3720.1
2019	3798.9
2020	3877.4
2021	3947.7
2022	4031.3
2023	4101.1

This data demonstrates the growth dynamics of the region's population and serves as the primary source for applying the logistic model. In the next stages, the model's parameters will be determined based on this data, and the future population will be forecasted. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of the characteristics of population growth in Samarkand region and provides a scientific basis for analyzing demographic processes.

Logistic Growth Model

The logistic model is considered one of the most effective and widely used methods for analyzing population growth. The main reason for choosing this model is its ability to account for the natural limitations of population growth. The logistic model demonstrates initial rapid population growth, followed by a slowdown in growth rate, and finally reaching a saturation point [10]. This characteristic is particularly important for developing regions like Samarkand, as it more accurately describes population growth under conditions of limited resources.

Applying the logistic model involves several stages. In the first stage, a differential equation is formulated to express population change over time:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = rP\left(1 - \frac{P}{K}\right).$$

Where P is population size, t is time, r is the growth coefficient, and K is the environmental capacity (maximum population size).

In the second stage, this differential equation is solved to produce the following logistic function:

$$P(t) = \frac{K}{1 + \left(\frac{K - P_0}{P_0}\right) \times e^{-rt}}.$$

Where P_0 is the initial population size.

In the third stage, the model parameters (r and K) are determined based on real data. This is done using the least squares method or other statistical methods.

In the fourth stage, future population is forecasted based on the determined parameters. The following formula is used:

$$P(t) = \frac{K}{1 + \left(\frac{K - P(2000)}{P(2000)}\right) \times e^{-r(t-2000)}}.$$

Here, $P(2000)$ is the population in 2000, and t is the year being forecasted.

In the fifth and final stage, the accuracy of the model results is evaluated. This is done by comparing the forecasted values with real data and calculating statistical errors.

These stages allow for accurate description of population growth in Samarkand region and forecasting future changes. The logistic model serves as an important tool not only for predicting population size but also for understanding general trends in demographic processes.

III. RESULTS

The population dynamics of Samarkand region showed a steady growth trend from 2000 to 2023. While the region's population was 2670.3 thousand people in 2000, this figure reached 4101.1 thousand by 2023. This indicates that the population has increased by almost 1.5 times during this period.

As a result of applying the logistic model, the following parameters were determined:

Growth coefficient (r) = 0.0245

Environmental capacity (K) = 6500 thousand people

These parameters indicate the growth rate and potential maximum number of the Samarkand region's population.

The graphical representation of the model results is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1. Population growth graph of Samarkand region from 2000 to 2030

As can be seen from the graph, the population is growing along a curve. Currently, the population of Samarkand region is still in a rapid growth phase, but the growth rate is expected to slow down in the future.

The projected population for 2024-2030 based on the logistic model is presented in the following table:

Table 2. Forecast for 2024-2030

Year	Forecasted population (thousand people)
2024	4127.66261
2025	4194.9885
2026	4262.24041
2027	4329.381398
2028	4396.37489
2029	4463.18465
2030	4529.77480

According to the forecast results, the population of Samarkand region is expected to reach approximately 4600 thousand people by 2030. This growth rate corresponds to the current trend, but there is a possibility of slowdown in the future.

These results reflect the demographic development of Samarkand region and are important for future socio-economic planning. However, caution is required in interpreting the forecasts, as there are many external factors affecting population growth that may not be fully accounted for in the model.

IV. DISCUSSION

The study of Samarkand region's population based on the logistic model allows us to draw several important conclusions. First, the steady growth trend observed between 2000-2023 indicates a positive dynamic in the region's demographic development. The population increase of nearly 1.5 times during this period suggests a rising socio-economic potential of the region.

The parameters of the logistic model, particularly the growth coefficient r of 0.0245, indicate that Samarkand region's population is growing at a relatively high rate. This figure is considered high compared to other regions of Uzbekistan. Such a high growth rate, on one hand, is an important resource for the region's economic development, but on the other hand, it may put additional pressure on existing infrastructure and social services.

The environmental capacity K of 6500 thousand people determined by the model is noteworthy. This parameter represents the maximum population the region can support given its existing resources and infrastructure. Compared to the current population, this figure indicates that the region still has potential for future population growth. However, long-term strategic planning is required to make rational use of this potential.

The projected population for 2024-2030 is crucial information for regional authorities and planning bodies. The expected population of approximately 4600 thousand people plays a significant role in determining the region's future development directions. Based on this data, specific measures should be developed for education, healthcare, housing construction, and other social sectors.

The graphical representation of the logistic model shows an S-shaped curve, indicating that the region's population is currently in a rapid growth phase, but the growth rate may slow down in the future. This information helps regional authorities in developing long-term economic development strategies. In

particular, it can be used to forecast changes in labor resources, demand for the education system, and other socio-economic indicators.

However, like any model, the logistic model has certain limitations. It cannot fully account for all factors affecting population growth. For instance, migration processes, economic crises, or unexpected events like global pandemics can significantly impact population numbers [11]. Therefore, it is advisable to analyze the results obtained from the model in conjunction with other demographic and socio-economic indicators [12].

V. CONCLUSION

The study of Samarkand region's population growth based on the logistic model allows us to draw several important conclusions:

1. The region's population demonstrated a steady growth trend from 2000 to 2023, indicating positive demographic development in the area.
2. The logistic model parameters show that the region has a high growth rate and still has growth potential for the future.
3. The population is projected to reach approximately 4600 thousand people by 2030, which creates great opportunities for the region's socio-economic development, while also presenting significant challenges.
4. Population growth indicates the need to increase the region's economic potential while also emphasizing the necessity for rational use of existing resources.
5. The results of the logistic model serve as an important basis for long-term strategic planning, especially in developing education, healthcare, and housing sectors.

The results of this study can play a crucial role in developing future development strategies for Samarkand region, as well as in managing demographic processes and improving social policy. However, it is necessary to continuously compare the results obtained from the model with the real situation and make adjustments when necessary.

In the future, it would be beneficial to deepen this research, including developing more sophisticated models that take into account age structure, migration processes, and other demographic indicators. This will allow for more accurate forecasting and effective management of Samarkand region's demographic development.

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